

Figure S1. Confident visits (#/24 h) in relationship to current applied to an electrified barrier for individual cattle. These feedlot cattle offered one of three treatments behind the electrified barrier: 1) AF: Alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), 2) TMR: total mixed ration (n=8) and 3) E: An empty bin (n=4). A confident visit was defined as an animal that approached the treatment bin, pushed against the barrier and dislodged it from the magnets. The barrier rose and the animal lowered their head into the bin for more than 1 s. The current applied to the barrier increased every 48 h so long as the steer continued to access the treatment (0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, 5000 μA ; maximum used by steers was 1250 μA). Values were summed by 48-h period and then divided by two to present on 24-h basis. Finally, a jitter feature is employed to make each individual easier to see at a given current.

Figure S2. Unsuccessful visits (#/24 h) in relationship to current applied to an electrified barrier for individual cattle. These feedlot cattle were offered one of three treatments behind the electrified barrier: 1) AF: Alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), 2) TMR: total mixed ration (n=8) and 3) E: An empty bin (n=4). The definition of an unsuccessful attempt was that an animal approached the treatment bin, pushed against the barrier but failed to dislodge it from the magnets. The barrier did not rise, and the animal was unable to access the bin. The current applied to the barrier increased every 48 h so long as the steer continued to access the treatment (0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, 5000 μA ; maximum used by steers was 1250 μA). Values were summed by 48-h period and then divided by two to present on 24-h basis. Finally, a jitter feature is employed to make each individual easier to see at a given current.

Figure S3. RIC registered visits (#/24 h) in relationship to current applied to an electrified barrier for individual cattle. These feedlot cattle were offered one of three treatments behind the electrified barrier: 1) AF: Alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), 2) TMR: total mixed ration (n=8) and 3) E: An empty bin (n=4). The feed bins automatically collected feeding behaviour data for all animals, including the number of times the animals successfully accessed the treatment diet, these visits are referred to as “RIC Registered Visits”. The current applied to the barrier increased every 48 h so long as the steer continued to access the treatment (0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, 5000 μA ; maximum used by steers was 1250 μA). Values were summed by 48-h period and then divided by two to present on 24-h basis. Finally, a jitter feature is employed to make each individual easier to see at a given current.

Figure S4. Intake of feed offered (%/24 h) in relationship to current applied to an electrified barrier that cattle had to push to access it. These feedlot cattle were offered one of three treatments behind the electrified barrier: 1) AF: Alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), 2) TMR: total mixed ration (n=8) and 3) E: An empty bin (n=4). The current applied to the barrier increased every 48 h so long as the steer continued to access the treatment (0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, 5000 μA ; maximum used by steers was 1250 μA). The daily % intake values were calculated by averaging the proportions from the 2 d in the 48-h period for each animal. Finally, a jitter feature is employed to make each individual easier to see at a given current.

Figure S5. The latency in minutes for finishing cattle to access treatments behind an electrified barrier for individual cattle. These feedlot cattle were offered one of three treatments behind the electrified barrier: 1) AF: Alfalfa hay chopped to 2.54 cm (n=5), 2) TMR: total mixed ration (n=8) and 3) E: An empty bin (n=4). The current applied to the barrier increased every 48 h so long as the steer continued to access the treatment (0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, 5000 μA ; maximum used by steers was 1250 μA). The latency values were calculated by averaging the two 24-h periods at each current level for each animal. Finally, a jitter feature is employed to make each individual easier to see at a given current.